

Plane Waves in Fourier Series of Wavefunction as Quasiparticles with Action-Reaction

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A quantum wavefunction can be written as a Fourier series and it is believed the $\exp(ikx)$ components represent actual plane wave solutions with different weights. It has been argued in previous notes, that a bound state is a resonance of these plane waves which carry different weight f_k . The system cycles through the different states with a frequency E as described by $\exp(iEt)$. It was also argued that $P(x \text{ intersection } p)$ equals $W(x) \int \sin(px)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and $\sin(px)$ is a combination of a forward and backward plane wave. It was argued that $\sin(px)$ physically models the motion of a particle with zitterbewegung and is present even in the absence of a potential. It was also noted that $W(x) \int \sin(px)$ described the motion of one of these plane waves in space. Summing over the various p values leads to $W(x)W(x)$ or the physical density. In classical physics, a particle has a velocity and potential energy at x_1 and different values at x_2 in accordance with energy conservation or Newton's law. The objective of this note is to examine how Newton's law is present in the motion of plane wave $W(x) \int \sin(px)$ in a bound quantum state.

Considerations from Statistical Mechanics of an Oscillator

Before considering the quantum system, let us briefly examine the statistical mechanical oscillator. It is argued in statistical mechanics, that there is a resonance, but it is one created by scattering of particles against particles, or in the case of sparse gas, particles against a wall at temperature T . This resonance is characterized by the Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$, although simply having a Boltzmann distribution does not guarantee a system is in a statistical resonance state. (Consider classical particles, with a Boltzmann distribution bouncing back and forth elastically between two walls without any interparticle scattering.) If a potential is added, the overall density is proportional to $\exp(-p^2/2mT) \exp(-V(x)/T)$. Thus, one still describes the system in terms of the scattering resonance with p representing the thermal momentum, not the overall momentum in the lab frame. (Landau has discussed such matters for the case of a gas in a rotating cylinder. (1)) Now $V(x)$ leads to collective kinetic energy which should be visible in sensitive enough experiments. In statistical mechanics, however, one coarse grains things and speaks of a density. For example, for a one dimensional oscillator, thermal particles should have lower collective kinetic energy near both walls and higher one in the middle where the potential $.5kx^2$ is zero. This should be visible in a sensitive experiment, but does not appear explicitly in $\exp(-p^2/2mT) \exp(-V(x)/T)$. In a previous note (2), we tried to examine how $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ might appear from considerations of collective velocity. The point we wish to make is that by using a density approach, details of physics, such as collective motion, may be obscured, but this does not mean they do not exist. We think this is also the case for a quantum mechanical bound state, although one does not have thermal energy.

Quantum Mechanics

We argued in (3), that one could consider a particle with zitterbewegung as being modeled by $\sin(px)$ (actually this is a combination of a forward and backward moving particle). If such a particle is placed in a potential, it will be scattered into various different momentum states, and these in turn will be scattered. We argued that a resonance is formed, described by $\exp(iEt)$ with a cycle frequency of E . Applying conservation to each point in space one could write:

$$\left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p \sin(px) \right] / \left[\sum_p f_p \sin(px) \right] + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

with $\left[\sum_p f_p \sin(px) \right]$, a normalization constant being called the wavefunction $W(x)$.

((1)) is equivalent to the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Thus, conservation of energy exists if one thinks of a kind of average kinetic energy given by the first term in ((1)).

It was argued in (3), that one could think in microscopic terms, by considering a plane wave in the system as described by $W(x) f_p \sin(px)$. The last two terms describe the weight for a particular momentum and zitterbewegung, and $W(x)$ is a space dependent amplitude. Summing over p one obtains $W(x)W(x)$ which is the physical density.

Plane Wave as a Quasiparticle?

The question that arises is how does one reconcile the picture of classical physics (Newton's second law) with a plane wave described by $W(x) f_p \sin(px)$. In classical physics, velocity is supposed to change as $V(x)$ changes. Here one p value is used for all x . This seems to be a complete contradiction. At this point, we wish to suggest that quantum mechanics is perhaps paralleling statistical mechanics where one has $\exp(-p^2/2mT) \exp(-V(x)/T)$. In such a picture, there is actually a collective velocity (in addition to p which is only thermal motion). It is this collective velocity which creates $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. Similarly in quantum mechanics, $W(x)$ may be associated with collective motion or Newton's second law. In quantum mechanics, however, p does not represent thermal motion, there is only translational motion. With zitterbewegung, however, it is argued that a particle bounces back and forth as it moves with average v in one direction, so matters are not straightforward.

Interaction of the Weighted Plane Wave with a Potential

As a first step, consider the interaction of a weighted plane wave with a potential. In classical physics, a moving particle interacts with a potential at a point x such that it has a potential energy of $V(x)$. If one has a density $d(x)$ in a little box, then potential energy is $V(x) d(x)$, with $V(x)$ representing the potential energy throughout the box. In quantum mechanics, one writes $V(x)W(x)W(x)$. What, however, is the potential energy of a weighted plane wave or quasiparticle $W(x) f_p \sin(px)$? To attempt to answer this, consider expanding $W(x)$ as a Fourier series. Then: $W(x) [\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)] = \sum_p' p' f_p [\exp(ip'x) - \exp(-ip'x)][\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)]$

In other words, one has a combination of all possible momentum plane wave states with a certain weight scheme. This seems to describe a plane wave p that is interacting with many other plane waves (just as $V(x)$ interacts with $W(x)$ in $V(x)W(x)$ in the Schrodinger equation with $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ both represented by Fourier series). Now each plane wave should interact with $V(x)$ in the usual classical mechanical way, namely $V(x) \exp(ikx)$. Summing over all p values i.e. $\sum_p W(x) V(x) \int p \sin(px)$ yields $V(x) W(x) W(x)$ which is the usual classical expression with density being represented by $W(x)W(x)$. Here, we see how it arises from the weighted plane wave. Thus, it seems that the weighted plane wave $W(x) \int p \sin(px)$ acts like a quasiparticle. It has momentum p , but $W(x)$ shows it is interacting at each point x with all of the other possible plane waves. It seems, however, that this "interaction" may be the result of averaging as quantum mechanics seems to be a statistical theory.

Newton's Second Law and a Weighted Plane Wave

One may next ask whether it is possible to see the effects of Newton's second law on the weighted plane wave $W(x) \int p \sin(px)$. At first, it appears that p stays constant for all x in direct contradiction of Newton's law (which indicates that p should change if there is a potential).

Let us start with $W(x) [p^2/2m + V(x)] \int p \sin(px)$

Consider first the changes in $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as one moves from x to $x+b$ where b is tiny. In other words, ignore changes in $\sin(px)$ for the time being. Then one has for the change (summing over p)

$$[d/dx W(x)] \int p^2/2m \int p \sin(px) + [d/dx W(x)] V(x) + W(x) [d/dx V(x)]$$

$d/dx W(x)$ is a flux as it can be written microscopically as $\sum_p p \int p \sin(px)$. Thus, the first term is a flux carrying the kinetic energy and leading to a density change. ($d/dx [W(x)W(x)] = 2 W(x) d/dx W(x)$). The second term is a density flux with the potential and the third term is associated with force or Newton's second law. Thus, it seems that Newton's second law is at work in the motion of a quasiparticle. Here we have just considered the weight $W(x)$ and how it changes, and this change includes both moving fluxes and Newton's force expression $-d/dx V(x)$. If one sums over p , one obtains:

$$Y(x) = -1/2m [d^3/dx^3 W(x)] + [d/dx W(x)]V(x) + W(x) d/dx V(x)$$

Now let us consider changes from $\sin(px)$.

These yield: $Z(x) = W(x)V(x) d/dx W(x) - W(x) 1/2m d^3/dx^3 W(x)$.

Using the time-independent Schrodinger equation gives:

$$Z(x) = - [d/dx V(x)] W(x) W(x) + W(x) E d/dx W(x)$$

Combining $Y(x)$ and $Z(x)$ one sees that the $d/dx V(x)$ terms cancel. Thus, there is a kind of action-reaction occurring. One obtains:

$2 E W(x) d/dx W(x)$ which is $d/dx [E W(x)W(x)]$ or the change in energy density.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that if one considers a weighted plane wave $W(x) \propto \sin(px)$ (this is actually a forward and backward wave interfering), then this plane wave seems to represent a quasiparticle with the $W(x)$ factor describing an interaction with other possible weighted plane waves at each point x . The weighted plane wave moves with a momentum p , but Newton's law is in the picture. $-d/dx V(x)$, the force, acts on $W(x)$, but also on $\sin(px)$ in such a way that the two cancel. Thus, there seems to be an action-interaction occurring.

References

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